

Deliverable 1.2

Specification for the assessment of data holders' maturity

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Work Package	WP1.4
Delivery Date (DoA)	30/09/2024
Actual Delivery Date	08/11/2024
Dissemination Level	PUBLIC
QUANTUM summary	<p>QUANTUM aims at developing and implementing a label mechanism that could be ideally adopted in the future HealthData@EU. QUANTUM builds on 5 technical work packages (WPs). WP1 conceptualises and provides technical specifications for a data quality, utility, and maturity label. WP2 designs and tests, at small-scale, the label. WP3 implements the labelling mechanism in a number of data holders. WP4 engages the data quality users' community; and, WP5 outreaches other interested parties, including other initiatives building HealthData@EU.</p>
Deliverable abstract	<p>This Deliverable "Specification for the assessment of data holders' maturity", addresses data holders' preparedness to manage data and data quality. Deliverable 1.2 covers the approach, methodology, findings and recommendations for the Data Holders' Maturity Model, resulting from QUANTUM task 1.4.</p>
Keywords	Data; Maturity; Secondary Use; Healthcare; Data Quality; Utility

Document Revision History			
Date	Version	Author/Contributor/Reviewer	Summary of Main Changes
16/08/2024	1.0	Monica Jones	Initial Draft
28/08/2024	1.1	Paola Quattroni / Alex Knight	First review
02/09/2024	1.2	Enrique Bernal-Delgado	Update from review
16/09/2024	1.3	Monica Jones	Further refinement
04/10/2024	2.0	Monica Jones	Update for Peer Review
23/10/2024	3.0	Monica Jones	Finalisation of the document

20/11/2024	3.1	Enrique Bernal	Inclusion of preface regarding article 78 EHDS Regulation
16/12/2024	3.2	Monica Jones	Addition in Section 5.1
13/02/2025	3.3	Ramón Launa	Minor adjustments: reference to final EHDS Regulation, etc
27/02/2025	3.4	Ramón Launa	Format: lato font
28/02/2025	3.5	Ramón Launa	Definition of data provenance changed

QUANTUM CONSORTIUM			
#	Short Name	Organisation Name	Country
1	IACS	INSTITUTO ARAGONÉS DE CIENCIAS DE LA SALUD	ES
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3	Health Data Hub	PLATEFORME DES DONNEES DE SANTE	FR
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3.2	HOSP TOULOUSE	CENTRE HOSPITALIER UNIVERSITAIRE DE TOULOUSE	FR
3.3	CHU Bordeaux	CHU HOPITAUX DE BORDEAUX	FR
4	I-HD	THE EUROPEAN INSTITUTE FOR INNOVATION THROUGH HEALTH DATA	BE
5	UCSC	UNIVERSITA CATTOLICA DEL SACRO CUORE	IT
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11	EUHA	EUROPEAN UNIVERSITY HOSPITAL ALLIANCE	BE
12	AP-HP	ASSISTANCE PUBLIQUE HOPITAUX DE PARIS	FR
13	VIB	VIB VZW	BE
14	CIPH	HRVATSKI ZAVOD ZA JAVNO ZDRAVSTVO	HR
15	HUS	HUS-YHTYMA	FI
16	THL	TERVEYDEN JA HYVINVOINNIN LAITOS	FI

17	ECRIN	ECRIN EUROPEAN CLINICAL RESEARCH INFRASTRUCTURE NETWORK	FR
18	BFARM	BUNDESINSTITUT FUR ARZNEIMITTEL UND MEDIZINPRODUKTE	DE
19	HIQA	HEALTH INFORMATION AND QUALITY AUTHORITY	IE
20	ISS	ISTITUTO SUPERIORE DI SANITA	IT
21	CESSDA ERIC	CESSDA ERIC	NO
21.1	KNAW	KONINKLIJKE NEDERLANDSE AKADEMIE VAN WETENSCHAPPEN - KNAW	NL
21.2	EKKE	ETHNIKO KENTRO KOINONIKON EREVNON	EL
22	e-helse	DIREKTORAT FOR E-HELSE	NO
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Accepted in Work Package Leaders' Group on 25 November 2024. The European Commission gives final approval to all QUANTUM's Deliverables.

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QUANTUM
THE HEALTH DATA QUALITY LABEL

Developing a data quality and utility label for the European Health Data Space.

Project number: 101137057
Call: HORIZON-HLTH-2023-TOOL-05
Topic: HORIZON-HLTH-2023-TOOL-05-09
Type of Action: Horizon-CSA
Start Date of Project: 01 January 2024
Duration: 30 months

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List of Abbreviations and Acronyms

CMM	Capability Maturity Model
EHDS	European Health Data Space
HDRUK	Health Data Research UK

1 Preface

Quantum approach: concepts

This deliverable, “Specification for the assessment of data holders’ maturity”, **addresses data holders’ preparedness** to manage data and data quality. Data quality, fit-for-use or fit-for-purpose are not addressed in this document. In the QUANTUM approach:

Maturity is a feature at the data holder level. It refers to the level of automation of data and data quality management procedures.

Quality refers to features that describe the content of a dataset, typically completeness, uniqueness, accuracy, validity, timeliness, and consistency of the data.

Fit-for-use is equivalent to a dataset's “potential” utility, typically information that describes the dataset in a standard manner, such as source, provenance or lineage, content, distribution, etc. Fit-for-use talks about the “potential” utility of a dataset, while the actual utility can only be informed by the user experience—in QUANTUM, the actual utility is referred to as fit-for-purpose.

Fit-for-purpose refers to the actual utility of an accessed dataset according to the objective of the health data request. The information necessary to evaluate fit-for-purpose depends on the user’s experience. This information needs to be added to the description of a dataset as a fit-for-purpose meta-data.

Underlying principles leading to the QUANTUM Maturity label specification

QUANTUM's approach builds on several principles:

- The **quality and utility label specification** (see deliverable 1.1) **needs to be completed with information on data holders’ preparedness** for data management and data quality management.
- The maturity label specification should not be static; on the contrary, it **has to be able to capture data holders’ improvements** towards automation **over time**.
- The maturity label **has to be applicable to any potential data holder**. This implies that the specification has to use a generic approach to data quality management.
- The label specification **has to cover the provisions of Article 78** in Chapter IV of the European Health Data Space Regulation. This deliverable has focused on letters c (data quality management), e (access and provision), and f(data enrichment) in paragraph 3, which are specific for data holders' maturity. Please note that letters a (data documentation), b (technical quality) and d (coverage) have been addressed in deliverable 1.1.

- The label specification will be flexible to allow capturing different levels of maturity for those datasets held by the same data holder.

2 Background

This Work package (WP) brings together the necessary conceptual grounds and evidence for an EHDS data quality and utility label focusing on evaluating the quality of the data *per se* and the maturity levels of data holders' organisations. Following desk-based research and expert consultations we have carried out a formal consensus process with the aim of agreeing on a label specification that will define the HealthData@EU standard and that is interoperable with existing meta-data documentation standards and future Health Dataset Catalogues.

The WP is composed of 4 tasks: Task 1.1 has conceptualised data quality and utility and establishes the questionnaire for the consensus methodology; task 1.2 has conducted a consensus process to get a common view of the relevant dimensions for the data quality and utility label; task 1.3 has operationalised the consensus, together with the in-depth knowledge from task 1.1, into a specification of the data quality and utility metrics; and task 1.4 has developed a maturity model for data holders in which the label will be embedded. The leadership for this work package is shared jointly between IACS and Health Data Research UK (HDRUK).

Finally, it is important to note that the QUANTUM label specification will contain elements addressing all fit-for-use (potential utility), technical quality and data holders' maturity. The specification will be tested and piloted with QUANTUM stakeholders (small-scale in WP2 and mid-scale in WP3). Ultimately, the label specification will be integrated as part of the dataset's cataloguing procedures at HealthData@EU. This report (D1.2) covers the approach, methodology, findings and recommendations for the Data Holders' Maturity Model, resulting from task 1.4.

2.1 Data Holders' Maturity Model

The quality and utility label of the datasets has to be embedded in the data holders' maturity process. Based on maturity models like the Capability Maturity Model (CMM), this task proposed levels of maturity for those dimensions affecting data management and data quality management. A dedicated focus group with data managers and data quality managers from the participating data holders was convened and asked to assess:

- key processes in data quality management enabling the production of a trusted data quality and utility label;
- goals to achieve in each process;
- implementation features that are common to all data holders;
- key practices, in particular those practices key in terms of data quality management

- sustainability;
- and levels of maturity.

In the primary data collection, participants represented different levels of maturity. Whilst no formal assessment was done at this stage, the discussion facilitated their experiences, which were then captured in the dimension definitions.

As in the case of the specifications for the data quality and utility label (Deliverable 1.1 of QUANTUM), there was a need for a consensual approach. The decision on the maturity levels was discussed with the same participants as in the focus group. The reference models were the Capability Maturity Model (CMM) (which is explained in more detail in the next section) and the Health Data Research UK (HDR UK) Data Maturity Model¹.

As a final discussion, once levels of maturity were decided, an agreement on how to assess the maturity level has been reached. For example, if the levels are 1-Initial (no quality procedure in place), 2-Repeatable, 3-Defined, 4-Managed and 5-Optimised (efficient), levels 1 and 2 could be evaluated via self-assessment, while levels 3 to 5 could require external certification.

External certification of the data maturity model assessment could occur through an independent third-party auditor or certification body that evaluates an organisation's data processes, governance, and maturity levels against the framework. This involves thorough reviews, documentation audits, interviews, and performance evaluations to ensure alignment with best practices and industry standards. Upon successful completion, the organisation receives formal certification, validating its data maturity status.

The output of task 1.4 confirmed the deliverable 1.2 (D1.2).

2.2 Understanding Maturity Models

Maturity models are frameworks that describe the progression of an organisation's processes from ad-hoc and chaotic to mature and disciplined. They provide a structured path for continuous improvement. The purpose is to help organisations assess current capabilities, guide systematic process improvement and enable benchmarking and best practices adoption.

The Capability Maturity Model (CMM) was developed by the Software Engineering Institute (SEI) at Carnegie Mellon University.² Initially, it was designed for software development, but it has now been adapted for various domains.

¹ [Development of a data utility framework | BMJ Health & Care Informatics](#)

² [Capability Maturity Model \(CMM\)](#)

2.2.1 Relevance to Data Management

Capability Maturity Models allow structured growth by helping to systematically enhance data management practices. There is usually an assessment tool that assists in identifying current data management capabilities. Continuous improvement encourages ongoing enhancement of data processes. Benchmarking also provides a framework for comparing with industry standards. Possible benchmarking models that could be adopted are the United Kingdom Benchmarking Index (UKBI) or the European Union equivalent, considering the diversity of models and the current need to standardise approaches in health data.

There are a number of benefits to this approach; these include improved data quality, enhanced decision-making, greater efficiency, and reduced risks.

3 Approach

3.1 Focus Groups

Data holders in QUANTUM were invited to participate in this decision process. Two focus group meetings were held. They were conducted online and facilitated by the co-leads of this task. The first one was held on 29/05 with 14 experts³ and second one on 19/06 with 15 experts.⁴ The sessions lasted for two hours, and the agenda was as follows:

³ Sciensano, Erasmus MC, THL, APHP, HIQA, HUS, KNAW, EUPH, ISS, EEKE, UKDS, eHealth Directorate Norway, HDH, HDRUK, IACS

⁴ THL, APHP, HIQA, HUS, KNAW, ISS, eHealth Directorate Norway, HDH, EUHA, CESSDA ERIC, HDR UK, IACS

- **Introduction and Welcome**
Overview of the focus group's objectives and agenda.
Introduction of participants and facilitators.
- **Background and Context**
Presentation on the EU quality and utility label initiative and the need for a data holders' maturity model.
Explanation of maturity models like the Capability Maturity Model (CMM) and their relevance to data management.
- **Identification of Key Processes in Data Quality Management**
Discussion on essential processes enabling the production of a trusted data quality and utility label.
Identification of goals to achieve in each process.
- **Common Implementation Features Across Data Holders**
Exploration of implementation features that are common to all data holders.
Sharing of best practices and challenges in implementing these features.
- **Key Practices for Data Quality Management Sustainability**
Identification and discussion of key practices crucial for sustaining high data quality management standards.
Strategies to integrate sustainability practices into existing workflows.
- **Assessment of Maturity Levels**
Evaluation of maturity levels in primary data collection among participants.
Identification of factors contributing to maturity levels and areas for improvement.
- **Proposal of Maturity Levels**
Collaborative development of maturity levels for dimensions affecting data management and data quality management.
Consensus building on proposed maturity levels and criteria.
- **Perspectives in Maturity Model Development**
Deliberation on the importance of perspectives shaping the maturity model.
Exploration of specific considerations in data management maturity.
- **Validation and Feedback**
Validation of the proposed maturity model through participant feedback.
Iterative refinement based on input received.
- **Next Steps and Conclusion**
Summary of key insights and outcomes from the focus group discussions.
Agreement on next steps for further development and implementation of the maturity model.

Half of the agenda was covered in the first group session and the remaining half in the second session. The maturity model matrix was created after the first session and updated during the second session.

3.2 Survey

Following two very successful focus groups, the maturity dimensions (i.e., the different elements that should be considered when assessing data holders' maturity) were confirmed by an online survey. The participants were invited to complete the short survey as contributors to the definition of the QUANTUM maturity model. The objectives of the survey were to:

- 1) have a sense of the level of agreement with the definitions discussed in the focus group;
- 2) to get some sense of the level of agreement on how relevant was a dimension in the measurement of the maturity of a data holder.

The participants were invited to cast the votes on a 1 to 9-point scale, where 1 represented "full disagreement" and 9 represented "full agreement". For each dimension, participants were given the possibility to provide comments that could help to interpret their vote.

Examples of the survey responses are shown below:

Data collection as "the level of definition of the processes capturing data for secondary purposes"
10 responses

Figure 1 - Survey response example for data collection definition

How relevant data collection is when measuring data holders maturity?

10 responses

Figure 2 - Survey response example for data collection relevance

4 Results

In total there were eleven responses to the survey. Each participant provided their level of agreement on the definition for each dimension and how relevant each dimension was when measuring the data holder’s maturity. Overall there were high levels of consensus on the dimensions. All of the comments were responded to and where relevant incorporated into the maturity model matrix.

The following graph shows the average agreement score on the definition for each of the dimensions presented in the survey.

Figure 3 - Average agreement score on the definition for each of the dimensions

Overall there were high levels of consensus on the dimensions. It can be seen that the survey respondents scored their agreement as high (>7) for most of the dimension definitions; the lowest agreement was seen for the definitions of “Data Access” (with a score of 6.7) and “Data Collection Process” (with a score of 5.5).

The following graph shows the average agreement score on the relevance for each dimension in the survey:

Figure 4 - Average agreement score on the relevance for each dimension

It can be seen that most of the dimensions were scored as highly relevant (>7) with the exception of Data Access, which was scored on average as 6.2.

The full survey with responses can be found in Annex I

5 Conclusions

5.1 Data Holders' Maturity Matrix

Following the focus groups and the dimensions survey the maturity matrix was updated and distributed for final review. The resulting data holders' maturity matrix format is provided below:

Serial	Dimension	Definition	Level 1	Level 2	Level 3	Level 4	Level 5	Reference	Comments
			Initial: a new or undocumented process, unpredictable, poorly controlled and reactive	Emerging (or Documented, Structured): the process is documented sufficiently so repeating the same steps may be attempted	Defined: the process is defined and confirmed as a standard process	Managed: the process is quantitatively and proactively managed in accordance with agreed-upon metrics	Optimised: process management includes deliberate process optimisation		
1	Data collection process	The processes relating to the capture of data from multiple sources for secondary purposes	No data collection or capture process for secondary purposes	Ad hoc processes exist for data collection	Defined processes exist for some data collection	Defined processes exist for all data collection and are used for secondary purposes	Processes are automated for all data collection, focus on continuous process improvement.	ISO 8000-62 data maturity model	
2	Data management - governance	The level of maturity of the data management processes	No documented data management governance	A documented data management plan covering collection, auditing, and management is available for the dataset	Evidence that the data management plan has been implemented is available	Demonstrated compliance with the data management plan	Externally verified compliance with the data management plan	Adapted HDRUK	Covers more than just data management planning
3	Data management - infrastructure	The level of implementation and development of the data holder's data management infrastructure	No data management infrastructure	An emerging data management infrastructure, some validation and verification	Data management infrastructure defined and confirmed as a standard process	Data management infrastructure, with partially automated, verified and validated (real time) data management	A robust and comprehensive data management infrastructure, with fully automated, verified and validated real time data management	European Health Data Space / FAIR	Cover security of infrastructure (throughout the dimensions)
4	Data provenance	Clear description of the lineage of the dataset providing transparent and comprehensive documentation of the data pipeline to get the dataset	No documented provenance	Source of the dataset is documented	Source of the dataset and any transformations, rules and exclusions	All original data items listed, all transformations, rules and exclusion listed and impact of these	Ability to view earlier versions, including "raw" or "source" dataset, and review the impact of each stage/step	Adapted HDRUK	
5	Data access	How well defined and implemented are data access processes, from a legal, ethical and technical perspective	No data access processes or procedures	Have the processes and procedures but don't respond in timely and consistent manner	Have the processes and procedures, and respond in timely and consistent manner	Data access system that covers both technical and policy areas, in accordance with agreed metrics	A comprehensive data access system that covers technical, ethical and policy areas (allowable uses, API documentation, access and approvals) compliant with EU Policy	European Health Data Space / FAIR	Cross reference to EHDS Trusted Data Holder
6	Data analytics environment	Analytical services, tooling and access to [secure] data environments	No data environment available	Requested analysis can be undertaken by internal teams and provided back in an anonymised format to data requestors	The dataset can be used in a secure data environment (SDE)	The dataset can be used in an SDE and other data and tools can be brought in as required	The dataset can be used in federated organised environment	Adapted HDRUK	
7	Data enhancement - augmentation	The application of various techniques to make data more useable for specific purposes	No data augmentation	Some techniques to make data more useable for specific purposes	Defined techniques to make data more useable for specific purposes	Managed techniques to make data more useable for specific purposes	Comprehensive application of various techniques and mapping to data model i.e. OMOP to make more useable for specific purposes	OMOP / OpenEHR / HL7 FHIR / ISO/IEC 22989:2022	This is different from Data enrichment. They are both subtypes of Data Enhancement.
8	Data enhancement - enrichment	Data sources enriched for example with annotations, image labels, phenomes, derivations, NLP derived data labels	The data has no additional derived fields, or enriched data.	The data include additional derived fields, or enriched data.	The data include additional derived fields, or enriched data used by other available data sources.	The derived fields or enriched data were generated from, or used by, a peer reviewed algorithm.	The data includes derived fields or enriched data from an [inter] national report.	Adapted HDRUK	This is different from Data augmentation. They are both subtypes of Data Enhancement.
9	Data Model	Availability of clear, documented data model that provides structure and standardisation	There is no data model	Known and accepted data model but some key field uncoded or free text	Key fields codified using a local standard and updated over time	Key fields codified using a national or international standard and updated	Data Model conforms to an [inter] national standard and key fields codified using a national / international standard	Adapted HDRUK / OMOP / OpenEHR / HL7 FHIR	Interoperability and Standardisation
10	Data Dictionary	Provided documented data dictionary and terminologies	No Data Dictionary	Data definitions available	Definitions compiled into local data dictionary which is available online	Dictionary relates to national definitions	Dictionary is based on international standards and includes mapping	Adapted HDRUK / EHDS	Link to Metadata Standards and Definitions

The resulting Data Holder's Maturity Model consists of ten dimensions to allow Data Holder's to assess their maturity. Each dimension has a definition that was refined through the focus group activity and follow up survey. There are 5 levels of maturity for each dimension with detailed criteria for each level. This forms a scale from lower to higher maturity. To use the matrix, users should take each dimension in turn and assess the maturity as objectively as possible. It could also be useful to introduce a practical example of assessment and classification by the Data Holder, something like a User Story from the perspective of the Data Holder.

Once the level of maturity has been assessed for each dimension it will provide a score from 1-5. Consequently, the overall score (compiling the scores obtained for each dimension) will be between 10 and 50. Supporting narrative should be provided to complement the scoring for each dimension. This should provide clear, evidence-based explanations for each score. It should highlight specific practices, tools, and processes in place, describe recent initiatives or improvements, and reference any relevant metrics or benchmarks. The narrative should also explain any gaps or challenges that influence lower scores, along with planned actions for improvement, ensuring transparency and context for the scoring decisions.

The Maturity Model is to be applied at an organisational level so only one assessment is expected from each Data Holder. There may be exceptional circumstances where the maturity for different domains are significantly different. In this scenario the Data Holder can opt to complete more than one maturity assessment for their organisation, making it clear which pipelines and/or datasets this refers to.

5.2 Next Steps

This report has been reviewed and cross referenced to other QUANTUM deliverables.

The Data Holders' Maturity Model will be further developed into a standalone tool that will be piloted and implemented as part of the ongoing work of WP2 and WP3 . User documentation and use cases will be developed for this maturity model. The Data Holders' Maturity Model will form part of the label specification foreseen in article 78 -Data quality and Utility label- in the current HealthData@EU Regulation.

Annex I

Survey on

Dimensions for the assessment of data holders' maturity

Instructions

You are invited to participate in this short survey in your capacity as a participant in the definition of the QUANTUM maturity model.

After the two focus groups, held on-line the 29th of May and the 10th of June, we discussed on 10 potential dimensions for the assessment of data holders maturity and on 5 levels of maturity.

In this short survey, we would like to 1) have a sense of the level of agreement with the definitions discussed in the last meeting; and 2) get some sense of the level of agreement on how relevant is dimension “x” in the measurement of the maturity of a data holder?

You are invited to cast your vote, on a 9 point scale, where number 1 is “full disagreement” and 9 is “full agreement”. For each dimension, you are also given the possibility to provide some comment that could help to interpret your vote

Survey results

Data collection as “the level of definition of the processes capturing data for secondary purposes”

11 respuestas

How relevant data collection is when measuring data holders maturity?

11 respuestas

Data management governance as “the level of maturity of the data management processes in place”

11 respuestas

How relevant data management governance is when measuring data holders maturity?

11 respuestas

Data management infrastructure as “the level of implementation and development of the data holder's data management infrastructure”

11 respuestas

How relevant data management infrastructure is when measuring data holders' maturity?

11 respuestas

Data provenance as “the level of detail in the description of source and history of a dataset, providing a transparent data pipeline”

11 respuestas

How relevant data provenance is when measuring data holders' maturity?

11 respuestas

Data augmentation as “the application of various techniques to make data more useful for specific purposes”

11 respuestas

How relevant data augmentation is when measuring data holders' maturity?

11 respuestas

Data access as “how well defined and implemented are data access processes, from a legal and technical perspective”

11 respuestas

How relevant data access is when measuring data holders' maturity?

11 respuestas

Data analytics environment as “how well defined and implemented are analytical services, tooling and access to secure data environments”

11 respuestas

How data analytics environment is when measuring data holders' maturity?

11 respuestas

Data enrichment as “how well prepared are data holders to enrich datasets with annotations, image labels, phenomes, derivations, NLP derived data labels”

11 respuestas

How relevant data enrichment is when measuring data holder's maturity?

11 respuestas

Data Model availability as “the existence of a clear and documented data model”

11 respuestas

How relevant Data Model Availability is when measuring data holders' maturity?

11 respuestas

Data Dictionary Availability as "the existence of documented data dictionaries and terminologies"

11 respuestas

How relevant Data Dictionary Availability is when measuring data holders' maturity?

11 respuestas

